

Policy appropriation¹ in teacher retention and attrition: the case of North-West Province

NOLUTHO N. DIKO

Human Sciences Research Council, Pretoria, South Africa

ndiko@hsrc.ac.za

MOEKETSI LETSEKA

University of South Africa, Pretoria

We report on the 2008 study by the Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC) on teacher retention and attrition in South African public schools, with a focus on North-West Province. Data from the study show that some teachers prefer to leave the teaching profession for promotion posts in non-teaching areas within the education sector, while others leave the education sector altogether for the private sector. There is evidence though, that despite concerns about the adequacy of teacher supply, South Africa has enough teachers to meet current teacher demands. The estimated 5.5% teacher attrition rate, the insufficient production of teacher graduates by universities, and the increasing number of teachers ready and willing to leave the teaching profession should they receive better job offers, are unlikely to compromise the supply, or the current pool of teachers. The greatest threat to the retention of teachers in the teaching profession appears to be ways in which provincial and regional education offices appropriate teacher appointment policies and procedures. We argue that teacher recruitment and appointment procedures are open to abuse.

Keywords: appropriation; education policy; North-West Province; teacher retention

Introduction

The issue of supply and demand of teachers is highly contested. Opinions vary among teacher unions, the Department of Education (DoE), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), and independent education researchers. While teacher unions contend that there is a shortage of teachers, the DoE (2007a) posits that “most research studies indicate an impending shortage of teachers in the country, although its exact magnitude is a matter of debate”. The DoE argues that there is clearly a lack of fit between overall demand and supply, and also between demand and supply for particular skills in particular schools; there is an over-supply in some subject areas, and an under-supply in others, as well as imbalances in the deployment of teachers, especially to rural schools. The ILO (2005) does not find the teacher shortage thesis convincing. It argues that there are no current quantitative shortages, but that shortages could be looming, given the large numbers of departures from teaching and the continually small intake to teacher training programmes.

The above contestations bring the challenges of attrition into the equation. Boe, Bobbott and Cook (1993:9) argue that public school teachers who leave the public school constitute the attrition component. They investigated attrition in the United States in terms of (a) reasons given by leavers for exiting the teaching profession, (b) occupational status of leavers in the year after leaving public school teaching, and (c) plans of leavers to return to teaching (Boe, Bobbott & Cook, 1993).

In this paper we draw on the 2008 study by the Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC), on retention and attrition of teachers, in which we were field researchers. While much has been written on the attrition of South African teachers through transnational migrations,² our focus here is on teacher attrition in North-West Province. Our contention is that while policies are often formulated with the best of intentions, their success or failure depends on how they are appropriated at grassroots level. Policy appropriation presupposes taking policy and making it one’s own (Sutton & Levinson, 2001:3). Appropriation is contrary to implementation, which is often a top-down

process. We argue that unless there is a tacit understanding on the fit and purpose of policy at provincial level, as well as transparency and fairness in actual policy implementation, such fit and purpose may not be realised.

This paper is in six sections. The introduction forms the first part and section two, which follows below, describes the research methodology. Section three briefly sketches the notion of policy appropriation. Our contention is that while education policy should be treated as a form of governance that is negotiated and reorganized at various levels, in South Africa it is the prerogative of the DoE. There is a taken-for-granted assumption that it should cascade to provincial, district, and regional levels. Section four teases out national education policy formulation. Section five explores ways in which education policy is appropriated in North-West Province, and maps out the implications of this for teacher recruitment, while section six sketches teacher attrition in North-West Province. We argue that while reasons for teachers to leave the teaching profession are real and we challenge the DoE to pay closer attention to improving teachers' conditions of service, the threat of attrition might not necessarily be as great as it is thought to be. In section seven we provide concluding remarks.

Research methodology

The research methodology was mainly qualitative and comprised structured interviews and focus group interviews. The aim of the interviews was to gather qualitative data on recruitment, retention and attrition of teachers. In short, to understand policy implementation.

During the second week of February 2008 we conducted interviews in four (4) schools in two districts of North-West Province — Mafikeng and Bojanala (Rustenburg). The schools visited were Barolong Secondary School and Leteane Secondary School in Mafikeng, and Matala Intermediate School and Reuben Monareng Primary School in Bojanala. In each school we interviewed an average of fifteen (15) teachers. The number of interviewees varied according to the size of the school and staff profile. We conducted focus group interviews with experienced teachers at each school — those with five or more years of teaching experience — and the number of participants varied between five (5) and eight (8); mathematics and science teachers, and language teachers. We also conducted structured interviews with school principals, deputy principals, non-teaching members of the school governing body, and district Area Programme Officers (APOs).

The following represent the core issues investigated:

- policies, practices and processes used to attract new entrants to teaching and to appoint new teachers;
- teacher retention policies and practices in the schooling system; and
- the nature of teacher attrition.

Furthermore, we obtained procedural documents from the APOs, such as “Procedures to be followed in the Filling of Posts of Head of Department, Deputy Principals and Principals as advertised in the Open Vacancy List No. 3 of 2005”, Departmental Circular No. 55, and “Open Vacancy List — Principal Posts (S8-S12), 2007”. We also obtained a 2007 Excel spreadsheet of data on “Education Attrition Rate, North-West Province” from the province’s Education Management Information System (EMIS) office in Mafikeng. We draw on these different datasets to make inferences. The information obtained from interviews with teachers was cross-checked against information obtained from interviews with principals, deputy principals and Department of Education officials. This enabled us to conduct a ‘thick description’ in the data analysis (Yin, 1993).

Conceptualising policy appropriation

Singleton (2005:10) argues that the policy process is traditionally viewed as a top-down operation in which central authorities identify problems, assign priorities, and design initiatives for educational change. She notes that centrally articulated blueprints are then implemented at lower levels of the policy ladder. For a long time policy implementation was seen as a straightforward task that simply

involved following the detailed plans that had been designed at the top. In South Africa this is still the case. Educational policy formulation is the prerogative of the National Department of Education. Policy implementation, is, however, driven by provincial departments of education, which in turn issue directives to the regions and districts on what is to be implemented, how it should be implemented, and when it should be implemented. Sayed and Jansen (2001) argue that it is in this devolved state that an active process of policy appropriation manifests.

Sutton and Levinson (2001:1) conceive of policy as “a complex social practice, an ongoing process of normative cultural production constituted by diverse actors across diverse social and institutional contexts”. They argue that policy is a form of governance that is constantly negotiated and reorganized at various levels throughout its life. For Koyama (2004:404), policy is applied in particular ways to specific situations, and there is a ceaseless interaction in which the social actors, policy, and situation inform one another.

In this paper we recognise that while the national DoE formulates educational policies, the provinces, regions, districts and SGBs appropriate the national blueprints to enact their own rules and regulations, which spell out conduct, procedures and principles, thus giving policy a new life. As Sutton and Levinson (2001:17) point out, the appropriation of educational policy emphasises the agency of local actors in interpreting and adapting such policy to the situated logic of their contexts of everyday practices. Thus appropriation of policy gives rise to new kinds of local normative policies and guidelines. The context in which policies are appropriated, who appropriates them, and what their interests might be, all influence policy outcomes to a large extent (Diko, 2004). The act of implementing a policy should therefore not be misconstrued to imply that the provinces simply receive, accept, and follow the intent or spirit of the policy. On the contrary, they can adapt or resist it, and these are legitimate acts of appropriating and reinventing it to suit their specific contextual realities.

Policies on recruitment and appointment

In this section we sketch selected policies on the recruitment and appointment of teachers with a view to understanding the interaction between the policy framework and the contextual factors, and how they impact on the teacher labour market.

Beyond the Labour Relations Act of 1995 and the Basic Conditions of Employment Act of 1997, which regulate the employment of all civil servants, the employment of teachers and their conditions of service are further regulated by laws and policies such as the South African Schools Act (SASA), No. 84 of 1996, the National Education Policy Act, No. 27 of 1996, and the Employment of Educators Act, No. 76 of 1998. The South African Council for Educators Act, No. 31 of 2000 monitors teachers' code of conduct. The National Policy Framework for Teacher Education and Development (2007) provides guidance on ensuring the availability of effective and efficient teachers, while the National Norms and Standards for School Funding (1998) sets out the national norms and minimum standards for school funding in terms of the SASA. It can therefore be reasonably argued that the overarching aim of education legislation and policies is to regulate the teaching profession to ensure the provision of an effective and efficient teaching corps.

The Employment of Educators Act of 1994 provides for the establishment of posts by provincial governments and assumes this will be done in collaboration with trade unions, which are members of the Education Labour Relations Council (ELRC), as well as the SGBs. The act provides guidelines on a wide range of employment-related matters such as the appointment, promotion, transfer or secondment of teachers; the required minimum qualification for teachers; teacher workload, and responsibilities for teachers. The South African Council of Educators (SACE), which was set up in 1996, is responsible for teacher registration, discipline and conduct, and professional development (Sayed, 2002:384), while the Employment of Educators Act of 1998 also provides detailed guidelines to principals and departmental officials who are required to conduct investigations in cases of alleged misconduct.

The National Policy Framework for Teacher Education and Development provides “an overall strategy for the successful recruitment, retention, and professional development of teachers” (DoE, 2007a:1). It aims to ensure that (a) teachers are properly equipped to undertake their essential and demanding tasks, (b) teachers are able to continually enhance their professional competences and performance, (c) appropriately qualified teachers fill all vacancies in schools, and there is a dynamic balance between demand and supply of teachers, (d) there is a community of competent teachers dedicated to providing education of high quality, with high levels of performance as well as ethical and professional standards of conduct, and (e) teachers are deservedly held in high regard by the people of South Africa.

Teacher recruitment in North-West Province

Inefficiencies in recruitment practices

The annual hiring cycle of teachers in public schools — from the moment the school principal reports the school’s staffing needs and shortages to the APO, to the point at which the teacher is officially appointed — takes a long time. This is often attributable to inefficiencies arising from provincial bureaucracy, as well as the lengthy processes and procedures. A case in point: upon receipt of the schools’ staffing needs and shortages the provincial education office compiles a list of all vacant posts in the province. The posts are then advertised in a government gazette, a departmental bulletin or circular, and in the public media. In the last instance, five qualifying applications are passed to the school for consideration. By the time the school principal and the SGB constitute the interviewing panel to interview the potential applicants between three to six months will have passed. In cases of deep rural schools that face enormous communication challenges, the process can take close to a year to complete. The lengthy time lag does not augur well for a healthy and sustained provision of teaching and learning. The pressure as a result of vacant posts is often absorbed by teachers in the system, who are already overloaded in regard to teaching and administrative allocations.

Recruitment and the quality of recruited teachers are driven by competition for salary packages between public schools, private schools and the private sector. It was evident from the interviews that schools with fully functional SGBs tend to attract highly qualified and specialist teachers, especially in key subjects, such as Mathematics and Science and Business and Commerce. In North-West Province such schools are located in the upmarket suburban areas of Rustenburg, or are linked to the mining industry. They service learners from families whose heads are mine employees and who have the resources to make substantial financial contributions to their respective schools’ budgets. This capacity gives the SGBs in the schools concerned the necessary financial ability to appoint additional teachers, especially in the Mathematics and Science and Business and Commerce fields, and to retain them. It was also evident from the interviews that schools located in the townships and rural areas often lack fully operational SGBs and service learners from previously disadvantaged backgrounds. They do not have sustainable budgets to make the much-needed SGB appointments.

The Area Programme Officer (APO) of Bojanala (Rustenburg) acknowledged that the province’s public schools are plagued by lack of capacity and general dysfunctionality, particularly in respect of parental involvement and participation in SGBs. She also acknowledged that the mines pose a serious threat to public schools in that they are not only aggressive in branding their schools and marketing the benefits and opportunities they offer qualified teachers,³ but they also offer competitive remuneration packages that far exceed packages offered by public schools.

In all four schools we visited some teachers were enrolled in some form of further study to upgrade their qualifications. Yet, contrary to aim (b) of the National Policy Framework for Teacher Education and Development (2007a), there was concern that they were wasting time and money given that qualifications are not recognised for remuneration or promotion. This caused much distress for experienced teachers who were studying towards master’s (MEd) and doctoral (PhD) degrees but were stuck at PL1 (see endnote 2). They were concerned (a) that they were investing huge amounts of their hard-earned money towards further education and development with no

assurance of return on investment (ROI), (b) that notwithstanding their extensive experience and qualifications they were overlooked for promotion posts, and (c) that there was therefore no reason why they should not leave the teaching profession. A Business and Commerce teacher surmised that investing in further study in modern-day South African education did not make business sense given that such an initiative was neither recognised nor rewarded. He likened such an investment to throwing money into the paper shredder.

The interviews with school principals, deputy principals, teachers, and members of the SGB, highlighted the concern that the teacher recruitment and promotion processes were open to abuse by powerful and influential role players such as teacher unions and education officials. It was reported that if a principal wants a particular candidate in his/her staff complement, he/she would tailor-make the requirements for the post to suit the preferred candidate. This would be followed by behind-the-scenes lobbying for the preferred candidate in the build-up to the interview, especially if the post is at PL2 or PL3. It was noted that while interview questions for appointment in posts are issued by the Education District Office and there is a veil of confidentiality that surrounds them, they are often leaked to the preferred candidates. Incidents, where preferred candidates recited answers to interview questions verbatim as they appeared in the memorandum, were common.

Temporary appointments

It was reported that most principals preferred to offer some of their staff temporary appointments. This is because temporary appointments are less cumbersome. They do not need to go through the arduous advertisement process, which is a requirement for permanent appointments. Once principals have identified their subject and staffing needs they can fill the post at their earliest convenience. Appointments are usually based on renewable three-month contracts depending on the school's staffing needs. While this route may be advantageous for principals, it is not a desirable option for teachers. It does not offer long-term job security and does not inspire the levels of commitment and accountability expected from teachers in permanent posts. Some of the teachers we interviewed reported that they had been on temporary appointments for over ten years. They were aware that their respective principals might be contravening sections of the Labour Relations Act of 1995, but were reluctant to challenge their conditions of appointment for fear of losing their jobs.

During the interviews we learned about acute staff shortages in key subject areas such as Afrikaans, English, Mathematics, and Science. The APO of Bojanala (Rustenburg) district noted that public schools were fighting a losing battle against mine schools for teachers in the above subjects. As mentioned earlier, mine schools offer highly competitive salary packages that public schools cannot match. The APO suggested that an alternative strategy under consideration was to recruit Mathematics and Science teachers from neighbouring Zimbabwe. There was no guarantee, however, that the expatriate teachers would not, ultimately, also be poached by the mine schools.

Teacher attrition in North-West Province

Information, obtained from the APOs of the Mafikeng and Bojanala (Rustenburg) districts and from the EMIS office in Mafikeng, suggests that North-West Province faces the challenge of teacher attrition, as defined by Boe, Bobbott and Cook (1993). However, this is not as yet a serious challenge. For instance, the DoE's (2007b) EMIS data show that in 2007 the province's headcount of teachers in "ordinary public schools" was 25,185. The North-West EMIS (2007b) estimates that 277 (or 0.01%) left the teaching profession. When these data are disaggregated by various exit options, 25 teachers took retirement packages under section 16 (1) (A) of the Public Service Act of 1994; 32 were deceased; 156 resigned; 1 retired under Article 16 (2) (A) of the Public Service Act 1994; 6 retired under Section 16 (4) of the Public Service Act of 1994; 24 took compulsory retirement packages under Section 10 (2) of the Educators' Employment Act of 1994; 15 took early retirement packages under Section 10 (3) (A) of the Educators' Employment Act of 1994, and 18 retired under section 10 (1) of the Employment of Educators Act of 1998 (see Table 1).

Table 1. North-West Province teacher personnel attrition by number, 2007

Exit type	Count of exit type
Retired under section 16(1) (A) Public Service Act	25
Deceased	32
Resigned	156
Retire under article 16 (2) (A) Public Service Act 1994	1
Retired (compulsory) under 16 (4) Public Service Act 1994	6
Retired under 10 (2) Educators' Employment Act 1994	24
Retired (early) 10(3) (A) Educators' Employment Act 1994	15
Retired under 10 (1) Employment of Educators Act 1998	18
Grand total	277

Source: Department of Education (EMIS), North-West Province, 2007

When the data are further disaggregated by race they show that the main drivers of the province's attrition in 2007 were resignations and retirements. In total, 156 teachers (68 Africans, 2 coloureds, 1 Indian, and 85 whites) resigned, while 89 teachers (67 Africans, 19 whites, 2 coloureds, and 1 Indian) retired (see Table 2). Eighty-five white teachers, against 89 African teachers, resigned, while 19 white teachers, against 67 African teachers, retired.

Table 2. North-West Province teacher personnel attrition by race, 2007

Resignation type	African	Coloured	Indian	White	Total
Retired under 16(1)(a) (Public Service Act 1994)	21	1		3	25
Deceased	30	1		1	32
Resigned	68	2	1	85	156
Retired under 16(2)(a) Public Service Act 1994				1	1
Retired (compulsory) 16(4) Public Service Act	1	1		4	6
Retired under 10 (2) (Educators' Employment Act 1994)	20			4	24
Retired (early) 10 (3) (a) Educators' Employment Act 1994	12			3	15
Retired under 10(1) (Employment of Educators Act 1998)	13		1	4	18
Grand Total	165	5	2	105	277

Source: Department of Education (EMIS), North-West Province, 2007

Table 3. North-West Province teacher personnel attrition by gender, 2007

Resignation type	Female	Male	Total
Retired under 16(1)(a) (Public Service Act 1994)	17	8	25
Deceased	16	16	32
Resigned	94	62	156
Retired under 16(2)(a) Public Service Act 1994	1		1
Retired (compulsory) 16(4) Public Service Act	5	1	6
Retired under 10 (2) (Educators' Employment Act 1994)	17	7	24
Retired (early) 10 (3) (a) Educators' Employment Act 1994	9	6	15
Retired under 10(1) (Employment of Educators Act 1998)	17	1	18
Grand Total	176	101	277

Source: Department of Education (EMIS), North-West Province, 2007

When the same data are disaggregated by gender, it becomes apparent that more females than males resigned from the teaching profession in 2007. For instance, 94 females against 62 males

resigned (see Table 3). The second important driver of the province's teacher attrition was retirement. A total of 66 females, against 23 males, retired. Thus more female teachers than males left the North-West teaching profession in 2007.

Considering only an estimated 0.01% of teachers left the teaching profession in North-West Province, it can therefore be reasonably argued that the teacher shortage thesis is not convincing (ILO, 2005). Indeed Paterson and Arends (2008:97) argue that "the number of graduates who completed degrees and diplomas in the field of education increased from 17,823 in 1995 to 28,755 in 2004, or nearly 61%".

This should not, however, detract from the fact that teachers are leaving the teaching profession and will continue to do so until the working conditions at schools are improved. Both the focus group interviews and structured interviews highlighted a wide range of reasons why teachers are eager to leave the teaching profession should alternative job opportunities arise. The main concerns raised during the focus group interviews were as follows:

- a perception that salaries in public schools are not market related;
- teachers complained that they were not sufficiently recognised for the arduous work they are doing, often under hostile conditions given the collapse of family values and lack of discipline among the learners;
- teachers crave recognition for staff development initiatives many of them undertake. We spoke to experienced teachers who were studying for master's and doctoral degrees but who were employed at Post Level 1;
- rapidly changing policies generated increasing volumes of paperwork;
- teachers expressed concerns regarding promotion policies for learners. Directives from regional offices required teachers to promote learners with average mean scores as low as 30%. As a result, learners who did not meet the requirements for promotion to the next level were, notwithstanding, promoted. Inevitably they struggled with the language and concepts, and created serious challenges for class teachers; and
- the DoE seems preoccupied with numbers to justify throughput at the expense of quality.

Conclusion

Teacher retention and attrition in South Africa raise serious and pertinent questions with regard to school governance. Our study suggests that we are probably witnessing merely a change in governance structures without the necessary transfer of real power to key role players in school governance. Some parts of education policy are accepted and accommodated, while others are resisted, appropriated or given new meaning. Our conclusion is that the change of structures alone cannot yield the desired cultural change in schools. The power to influence the process of employing teachers remains a thorny and highly contested issue. Participation by parents, as members the SGBs, in recruiting and employing teachers is often mere tokenism. While national policy is presumed to have devolved powers to communities to take ownership of school governance, the full involvement of communities is far from being realised. Control of processes in school governance continues to be vested in school principals and education officials. We can therefore reasonably argue that attempts to democratise school governance are failing. The ripple effect of this is an uninspiring teaching profession where the same old practices continue to be reshaped. The privileged groups — education officers, principals and union leaders — continue to consolidate their grip on the system for patronage favours through misappropriation of well laid out plans to democratise school governance. Educators are caught in the crossfire as carriers of the greatest burden of policy failings. It is no wonder they are ready to leave the profession.

Notes

1. Margret Sutton and Bradley Levinson (2001) prefer the term 'policy appropriation' to 'policy implementation' in their attempt to highlight the social nature of policy processes. They argue that policy in school

- settings has a long tradition of focusing on top-down policies set by government agencies.
2. Volume 25 Number 2 of Perspectives in Education, June 2007, is a Special Issue on transnational migration and recruitment of teachers from the education systems of Commonwealth member countries. The papers by Bertram *et al.* (2007), McNamara *et al.* (2007), De Villiers (2007), Manik (2007), and Waghid (2007) address the transnational migration of South African teachers.
 3. In this paper we use 'qualified teachers' to refer to teachers with Relative Education Qualification Values (REQV) 13 and above. REQV 13 refers to a teacher with matric plus three (3) years of professional training (DoE, 2007). We interviewed teachers in Mafikeng who hold Master's degrees in education (MEds), are registered for doctoral degrees (PhDs) with the North-West University or with the University of South Africa (UNISA), and have more than ten years of teaching experience but have remained at Post Level (PL) 1. Educator PLs rank as follows: PL 1 = ordinary educator, PL 2 = Head of Department, PL 3 = Deputy Principal, PL 4 = Principal.

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